

CUSP Workshop Series Human Risk Assessment

Workshop 3/3 Data Needs

Introduction to data sources ; eNanoMapper data types

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Nanosafety Data Interface / eNanoMapper

H2020 POLYRISK database

About POLYRISK | NANOREG2 | CALIBRATE | OMICS | PLASTICMAP | AMBITLRI |

Filters Active - 0

top <input type="text" value="Q"/> × AA↑ #↓ ^	endpointcate <input type="text" value="Q"/> × AA↑ #↓ ^	method <input type="text" value="Q"/> × AA↑ #↓ ^	endpoint <input type="text" value="Q"/> × AA↑ #↓ ^
ECOTOX 609	Acute toxicity - dermal 18	Acridine Orange (AO) 2	No data 159
ENV FATE 111	Acute toxicity - inhalation 47	ALAMAR BLUE 5	% DEGRADATION (TEST MAT. AN... 1
EXPOSURE 1	Acute toxicity - oral 51	AO 2	% TISSUE VIABILITY 1
P-CHEM 170	Acute toxicity - other routes 26	Automated hematology analyzer 20	%_OF_ALVEOLAR_EOSINOPHILIS... 1
TOX 823	Appearance 9	BAL cell celularity 5	%_OF_ALVEOLAR_LYMPHOCITES... 1

top ↑↓	endpointcategory ↑↓	method ↑↓	endpoint ↑↓	unit ↑↓
ECOTOX	Short-term toxicity to aquatic invertebrates	OECD TG 202	EC10	mg/L
ECOTOX	Short-term toxicity to aquatic invertebrates	OECD TG 202	EC25	mg/L
ECOTOX	Short-term toxicity to aquatic invertebrates	OECD TG 202	EC50	mg/L

<https://search.data.enanomapper.net/projects/{projectid}/summary/>

Nanosafety Data Interface / eNanoMapper

<https://search.data.enanomapper.net/projects/{projected}/dashboard/?spec=Overview>

Data model for materials and measurements

- Researchers routinely describe the main objects of their experiment, i.e., materials, methods and results, in the scientific literature.
- Computer representation of the experimental system, i.e., the materials, methods and results as domain objects and enabling machine actionality requires defining the data elements and the relationships and constraints between them.
- In computer science, this is known as a data model, and serves as a blueprint for how data will be stored, accessed, and manipulated

eNanoMapper Data model

Substance	Protocol application data: Comet	Endpoint	Result	Concentration	Treatment	Exposure time
Substance name: BASO4 NM-220 Substance UUID: NRG2-2b94afbdf44-3f76-ba5b-8973badd91b7 Public name: NM-220 Project: NanoReg2	Cell type: A549 Exposure time: 24 h, 3h Method: COMET SOP reference: link	NET FPG SITES	3.65 % tail	0 ug/ml	sample	24 h
			12.35 % tail	0.16 ug/ml		
			11.59 % tail	0.48 ug/ml		
			12.30 % tail	1.6 ug/ml		
			13.21 % tail	4.8 ug/ml		
			11.99 % tail	16 ug/ml		
	Input file: NR2_Scoring data_NILU_20210503.xlsx Number of technical replicates per conditions: 3	NET FPG SITES	13.75 % tail	48 ug/ml	sample	3 h
			6.94 % tail	120 ug/ml		
			12.31 % tail	160 ug/ml		
			3.29 % tail	0 ug/ml		
			5.82 % tail	0.16 ug/ml		
			5.29 % tail	0.48 ug/ml		
	NET FPG SITES	NET FPG SITES	5.95 % tail	1.6 ug/ml	sample	3 h
			7.32 % tail	4.8 ug/ml		
			6.33 % tail	16 ug/ml		
			15.85 % tail	48 ug/ml		
			12.11 % tail	120 ug/ml		
			13.48 % tail	160 ug/ml		

Substances. Composition. Measurements. Protocols. Assay. Investigation.

ECHA REACH dossiers (nonconfidential)

- an important source of information on already registered substances.
- <https://echa.europa.eu/information-on-chemicals>
- free download in IUCLID6 format at (updated every 6 months)
<https://iuclid6.echa.europa.eu/reach-study-results>.
- IDEA has an existing workflow of converting the IUCLID6 files and making them available in eNanoMapper compatible database
 - the LRI AMBIT tool, at <https://ambitlri.ideaconsult.net>

IUC Substance name: Reaction Mass Of 1,1'-Oxybis(Ethylbenzene) And Styrene, Oligomers
IUC Substance UUID: IUC6-d076f2ac-0c53-4823-908c-f98ae6227981
IUC Public name: Styrene Heavy Ends
Legal entity:
Legal entity UUID:
Type substance composition: multi-constituent substance/organic

IUC Substance Reference Identifier
 CAS:
 EC: 916-736-9
 Chemical name: reaction mass of 1,1'-oxybis(ethylbenzene) and styrene, oligomers,unnamed
 IUPAC name:
 UUID:
 IUC Flags:

Composition name: Reaction Mass Of 1,1'-Oxybis(Ethylbenzene) And Styrene, Oligomers
Composition UUID: L6-86565222-7e12-4b13-8329-b9d4e231a0d8

Type	Name	EC No.	CAS No.	Typical concentration	Concentration ranges			Structure
Constituent	1,1'-Oxybis(Ethylbenzene), Unnamed	272-620-1	68900-67-4	0 % (w/w)	0 % (w/w)	0 % (w/w)	Also contained in...	
Constituent	Styrene, Oligomers, Unnamed	500-008-9	9003-53-6	0 % (w/w)	0 % (w/w)	0 % (w/w)	Also contained in...	

Screenshot of a styrene substance in the eNanoMapper data model, with composition (top) and selected toxicity data (bottom)

Styrene Heavy Ends

7.2.1 Acute toxicity - oral (2)

Species	Endpoint	Value	Sex	Interpre of the results	Guideline	Study year	Owr	Reliability	UUID
-	LD50	(300, 2000) mg/kg bw	not specified	-		2014	-	2 (reliable with restrictions)	IUC6-t
rat	LD50	> 2000 mg/kg bw	female	-	OECD Guideline 423 (Acute Oral toxicity - Acute Toxic Class Method)	2015	-	1 (reliable without restriction)	IUC6-t

Showing 2 substance(s) (1 to 2) ◀ Previous Next ▶

ECHA REACH dossiers (nonconfidential)

“Plastic map” : polymers and substances compatible with polymers

- Worksheet S8-PlasticMap : 10763 substances with
 - identifiers (CAS, name, InChI, SMILES)
 - use related (function, compatible polymer, industrial sector)
 - regulatory information (tonnage).
- Worksheet S9-PlasticMap
 - additional information on a subset of 2485 substances of potential concern.
- From the supplementary information we used
 - the identifiers
 - the chemical composition information
 - the use related properties
 - (Polymer: Polymers that this substance might be compatible with, Function: Functions that this substance might fulfil, Industrial sector: Industrial sectors in which plastics including this substance might be used)
 - the hazard properties (summary)
 - the level of concern, defined in [1] to preliminarily prioritize substances.

PlasticMap [1] is a compilation of information from 63 data sources (scientific, regulatory and industrial) related to plastic. An Excel file with the compiled and well annotated information is provided as supplementary material [1] H. Wiesinger, Z. Wang, S. Hellweg, *Deep Dive into Plastic Monomers, Additives, and Processing Aids, Environ. Sci. Technol.* 55 (2021) 9339–9351. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c00976>.

Filtering REACH dossiers by “Plastic map”

A screenshot of the H2020 POLYRISK database interface showing the results of filtering by Plastic Map. The top navigation bar includes Home, Project, Search, FAIR Tools Guide, Template Wizard, Help, [n10705013], and Log out. The main content area is titled "H2020 POLYRISK database Substances search". There are several filter options: Polymer (PET), Function (Flame Retardant), and a dropdown menu for Plastic Map. The Plastic Map dropdown is open, showing a list of categories: Agriculture, Automotive, Building & Construction, Electrical and Electronic Equipment, Food-contact plastics, Household items, Hygiene and Medical items, Packaging, Textiles, Toys, and furniture and other. The first two options, "Choose..." and "*", are highlighted in blue. Below the filters, there are two rows of search results. The first row shows four results: 1163-19-5 (Benzene, 1,1'-oxybis[2,3,4,5,6]), 1306-19-0 (Cadmium oxide (CdO)), 1314-13-2 (Zinc oxide (ZnO)), and 25637-99-4 (Cyclododecane, hexabromo-). The second row shows five results: 1163-19-5 (Benzene, 1,1'-oxybis[2,3,4,5,6]), 117-81-7 (1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid), 32536-52-0 (Benzene, 1,1'-oxybis-, octabro), 1332-07-6 (Boric acid, zinc salt), and 7428-48-0 (Octadecanoic acid, lead salt (1)). Each result card displays the name, CAS number, and regulatory status (CMR, PBT) with a level of concern (high or medium). A blue arrow points to the Plastic Map filter, and another blue arrow points to the search results.

We used the PlasticMap substances as a filter to the REACH dossiers

Developed eNanoMapper compatible data service, allowing to present and query data through the same interface.

The REST API is used by the POLYRISK eNanoMapper database to build user interface accessing the data.

Substance search

The search interface shows a search bar with the query 'Polymer_ss:"PET" Function_ss:"Monomer"Industrial_Secto'. Below the search bar are several dropdown menus for 'Plastic Map', 'Monomer', and 'Textiles'. The 'Monomer' dropdown is open, showing a list of categories with 'PET' selected. Below the search results, a grid of substance cards is displayed, each with a chemical structure, name, and 'level_of_concern: high' status. Two blue arrows on the left point towards the search bar and the results grid.

Name	Chemical Structure	CMR Status	Level of Concern
123-31-9 1,4-Benzenediol	<chem>Oc1ccc(O)cc1</chem>	fulfilled	high
7631-86-9 Silica	<chem>[Si]</chem>	fulfilled	high
108-95-2 Phenol	<chem>Oc1ccccc1</chem>	fulfilled	high
12001-29-2 Mica-group minerals	<chem>[Si]</chem>	fulfilled	high
71-43-2 Benzene	<chem>c1ccccc1</chem>	fulfilled	high
100-42-5 Benzene, ethenyl-	<chem>C=Cc1ccccc1</chem>	fulfilled	high
1344-28-1 Aluminum oxide (Al2O3)	<chem>[Al]</chem>	fulfilled	high
50-00-0 Formaldehyde	<chem>C=O</chem>	fulfilled	high
107-13-1 2-Propenenitrile	<chem>C=CC#N</chem>	fulfilled	high
117-81-7 1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid	<chem>O=C(O)c1ccccc1C(=O)O</chem>	fulfilled	high

Substance similarity user interface with options to select Polymer, Function and Industry sector in addition to the free text search.

Similar substances appear at the bottom, on clicking the hits from the top search

Filtering REACH dossiers by “Plastic map” (1)

- We used the PlasticMap substances as a filter to the REACH dossiers
- Developed eNanoMapper compatible data service, allowing to present and query data through the same interface.
 - The REST API is used by the POLYRISK eNanoMapper database to build user interface accessing the data.
- In order to match the ECHA REACH data with PlasticMap , we developed a data workflow, which retrieves all substances, containing components listed in PlasticMap (and further uses it for data analysis).
 - Once these substances are retrieved, we can include in the analysis any data available in the REACH dossiers (e.g. physicochemical characterisation and hazard data).
 - For illustration purposes we only included water solubility data in the follow-up analysis, as well as molecular mass, calculated from chemical structure.

Filtering REACH dossiers by “Plastic map” (2)

- The main steps of the workflow are reading the PlasticMap data source,
- retrieving substances from ECHA dossiers for which at least one component is found in PlasticMap
- retrieving selected property data from ECHA dossiers,
- calculating molecular mass based on chemical structures,
- generating triples from the combined data,
- training a knowledge graph using the triples
 - *The combined PlasticMap and REACH dossiers knowledge graph contains over 80000 triples*
- updating the POLYRISK eNanoMapper search engine index using the substance vectors obtained.

Illustration of learned representations for substances in PlasticMap (dimensionality reduction UMAP algorithm used to reduce 512 d learned representation to draw 2D chart)

eNanoMapper Dashboard (plasticmap)

Interactive visualisation and filtering for substances in PlasticMap. Color by CMR property (red = not fulfilled, orange = fulfilled blue = not defined).

eNanoMapper Dashboard (plasticmap)

Interactive visualisation and filtering for substances in PlasticMap. Color by Bioaccumulative property

Summary

- eNanoMapper data model; interactive summary
- Used the PlasticMap substances as a filter to the REACH dossiers
- developed eNanoMapper compatible data service, allowing to present and query data through the same interface.
 - The REST API is used by the POLYRISK eNanoMapper database to build user interface accessing the data.
- Developed a a computational workflow to estimate multiple property-based similarity
 - based on the indications in the PlasticMap and data in the REACH dossiers, which enables to find substances w with similar properties in the database.
- **The same workflow can be applied to other existing databases of interest.**

Thank you!

Questions?